

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15376194>

OPERATING PRINCIPLE OF ASYNCHRONOUS GENERATORS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the operating principle of asynchronous generators and several relevant issues related to optimizing the control systems of electric drives. An analysis of energy losses in asynchronous electric drives is also presented

This paper discusses the structure and working principle of asynchronous generators. It explains their operation in different modes—motor, generator, and electromagnetic braking—based on rotor slip and speed. Due to their simple design, low cost, and reliability, asynchronous generators are widely used in industrial applications.

Key words: *Electric drive, frequency control, asynchronous motor, stator windings, stator and rotor currents, mechanical transmission device.*

Introduction:

Asynchronous generator – an asynchronous machine operating in generator mode that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy. The asynchronous generator is rotated at a high speed in the direction of the magnetic field using a driving motor. At this point, the slip of the rotor becomes negative, a braking torque is generated on the machine shaft, and it begins supplying energy to the grid, thus functioning as a generator. Asynchronous generators are used as low-power auxiliary power sources and braking devices.

Asynchronous motors form the basis of electric drives and are widely used in both

uncontrolled and automatic control processes across all sectors of the economy, including in large, medium, and small power electric equipment drives in mining, agriculture, and other fields. Although asynchronous machines are capable of operating in motor, generator, and electromagnetic braking modes, most are designed for motor operation. Squirrel-cage asynchronous motors, considered to be the most cost-effective and easiest to operate, have been the most commonly used type of electric motor in all sectors of the economy, despite their previously limited control capabilities. Wound rotor asynchronous motors, which allow speed control by varying rotor speed, are used in certain industries. However, with the rapid development of power electronics and electromechanics over the past 20–30 years, the possibility of frequency control has been unlocked. As a result, squirrel-cage asynchronous motors with frequency control are now increasingly being utilized across various sectors of the economy.

An asynchronous machine consists of two parts: a stationary part (stator) and a rotating part (rotor). The rotor is placed inside the stator. It comprises a shaft, a magnetic core (magnetic conductor), and either a squirrel-cage (multi-phase) winding or a three-phase winding placed in the slots on its outer cylindrical surface. The stator consists of a frame, a magnetic core, and one-, two-, or three-phase windings located in the slots on its inner cylindrical surface. The magnetic cores of both the stator and the rotor are assembled from thin laminated sheets made of special electrical steel.

Asynchronous motors are classified into two types based on the structure of the rotor:

1. Squirrel-cage rotor asynchronous motor;
2. Wound rotor (phase-wound) asynchronous motor.

Squirrel-cage rotor asynchronous motor – in this type, aluminum is cast into the slots of the rotor's magnetic core, forming winding conductors (bars), and the ends of these bars, outside the slots, are short-circuited on both sides by cast aluminum end rings.

Wound rotor asynchronous motor also consists of a shaft, a magnetic core mounted on the shaft, and a three-phase winding placed in its slots, each phase shifted

by 120° . The rotor phase windings are connected in a star configuration, and their terminals are connected to three slip rings (usually made of brass or copper alloy) mounted on one end of the shaft. These rings are connected to an external circuit through brushes.

When a three-phase voltage is applied to the stator winding of a three-phase asynchronous motor, a rotating magnetic field is generated in the stator with a synchronous speed of

$$n_1 = 60f / p \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency and p is the number of pole pairs.

The magnetic field lines cut through the stator windings and the rotor's squirrel-cage bars or three-phase windings, inducing electromotive forces (EMFs) in them. If the rotor winding is short-circuited, the induced EMF causes current to flow through the bars or windings. As a result of the interaction between the stator's rotating magnetic field and the rotor currents, an electromagnetic force acts on the rotor

windings. If the resulting electromagnetic torque is greater than the braking torque, it causes the rotor to rotate in the direction of the rotating magnetic field.

$$s = (n_1 - n_2) / n_1 \quad (2)$$

$$s = \frac{(n_1 - n_2)}{n_1} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Figure: 1 Structure of an Asynchronous Generator

Depending on the values of the stator magnetic field's rotational speed (n_1) and the rotor's rotational speed (n), an asynchronous machine can operate in motor, generator, or electromagnetic braking modes.

In the motor mode, the rotor speed is less than the speed of the rotating magnetic field generated by the stator ($n_1 > n$), and the slip is within the range $0 < s < 1$. In this case, the stator winding is supplied with electric energy from the power grid, and the rotor shaft delivers mechanical energy to a working mechanism. The machine converts electrical energy into mechanical energy.

If the stator winding is connected to the grid and the machine operates at the boundary slip of $s = 1$ (i.e., when the rotor is stationary, $n = 0$), it is called the short-circuit mode.

If the stator winding is connected to the grid and the rotor rotates at the same speed as the stator's rotating magnetic field ($s = 0$, i.e., $n = n_1$), then no torque is generated, because the rotating field does not cut through the rotor winding. This is known as the ideal no-load operation mode of the asynchronous machine.

If the rotor is driven (by some mechanical mechanism) at a speed greater than the rotating magnetic field speed ($n > n_1$), then the EMF, current direction, and slip in the rotor windings reverse. As a result, the electromagnetic torque (M) also reverses and becomes braking in nature, and the asynchronous machine switches to the generator mode. In this mode, the machine receives mechanical energy from a prime mover and converts it into electrical energy supplied to the grid. Here, the slip is within the range $0 > s > -1$.

If the rotor is rotated in the opposite direction of the stator's magnetic field, then

the EMF and active component of current in the rotor windings have the same direction as in motor mode, meaning the machine draws energy from the grid. However, the electromagnetic torque is directed opposite to the rotor's motion, causing it to brake. This is called the electromagnetic braking mode of the asynchronous machine. Since the rotor rotates opposite to the rotating magnetic field, its speed is $n < 0$, and slip ranges in $-1 < s < 1$. In this mode, mechanical energy is taken from the rotor, and electrical energy is consumed by the stator.

Electromagnetic braking mode is used in practice in cranes and hoisting mechanisms to reduce the speed during descent or stop quickly when necessary. To achieve this, the positions of any two phase wires connected to the stator winding from the grid are swapped, which changes the direction of the rotating magnetic field and produces a braking torque. Since slip is large in this mode ($s = 1$), the EMF and, consequently, the current in the rotor winding are also large. To reduce this current, a braking resistor (rheostat) is connected to the rotor winding in wound-rotor motors.

In industrial applications, asynchronous motors operating under nominal load typically have a slip s_n of about 3–5%, while in some special asynchronous motors, the slip can be 12–15%.

In conclusion; Asynchronous generators convert mechanical energy into electrical energy and can operate in motor, generator, and braking modes. Their performance is influenced by the rotor's slip, which determines the mode of operation. These generators are widely used in industries due to their simplicity, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. Recent advancements, including semiconductor converters, have further enhanced their functionality and applications.

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